

OPEN QUESTIONS

- How do we ensure that the use of third party platforms for anything that is created in a way that allows it to be shared or data conforming to FAIR principles, and meeting the Specimen Standard for Data of Collections?
- How might we support workflows for each content creator for volunteers and others who won't have direct access to museum's own social media accounts?
- How might each data entered with the social media data already in collection can be handled with that equipment with additional metadata from the relevant social media platform (just OAI)?
- How might IIP make it easier to manage, source and crop images from metadata user collections when preparing content for social media/blog?
- How might agencies such as IAH get access to analysis data about the resulting social media activity for analysis at all?

MAKING IT FAIR - TECHNICAL APPROACH

CONNECT & COLLECT FIND & SELECT USE & ENHANCE

